

IMPROVED ELECTRIC HEATING PROPERTIES OF EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITE FILMS CONTAINING MWCNTS

Fangxin Wang¹, Wenyan Liang²

¹ College of Aerospace and Civil Engineering, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin 150001, China
E-mail: wangfangxin@hrbeu.edu.cn

² College of Aerospace and Civil Engineering, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin 150001, China
E-mail: liangwenyan@hrbeu.edu.cn

Keywords: electric heating elements, electrical properties, MWCNTs, epoxy resin, composite films, rapid temperature response

ABSTRACT

Electrothermal materials, a kind of electrical resistor following Ohm's law, which convert electric energy into heat using multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) as fillers and polymer as matrix. In this research the electric and electric heating performances of the epoxy resin modified by the MWCNTs has been investigated. The epoxy/MWCNTs composite films containing different MWCNTs contents were fabricated by a laboratory-scale three-roll mill. we have investigated the use of a calendaring approach for dispersion of MWCNTs in epoxy resin, and the subsequent processing of MWCNTs/epoxy composite films. An electrical percolation threshold around 0.014 wt % MWCNTs in composite films was observed. The electrical resistivity of composite films varies from $\sim 10^{16} \Omega \text{ cm}$ for the neat composite films to $\sim 10^2 \Omega \text{ cm}$ of the composite films with 2.0 wt % MWCNTs owing to the formation of a conductive two-dimensional network of MWCNTs. The electrical transport properties of MWCNTs/epoxy composite films with 0.01-2.0 wt % exhibit linear behavior by obeying Ohm's law. Accordingly, the composite films were successful for the change from the insulator to the semiconductor. The electrical heating experiments of composite films with different MWCNT contents were carried out by varying applied voltages of 1-90V. In this research, the composite films containing 0.05-2.0 wt % carbon nanotubes show the excellent performance such as rapid temperature response, operational stability and high electric power efficiency at given applied voltage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins, which are also referred to as polyepoxides, are a class of reactive prepolymers and polymers which contain epoxide groups. They can be cross-linked either with themselves through catalytic homopolymerization, or with a wide range of hardeners such as multi-functional amines, acids, acid anhydrides, phenols, alcohols, and thiols. The cross-linking reaction, commonly known as curing, forms a thermosetting polymer with high mechanical properties, temperature and chemical resistance. Therefore, epoxy resins have a wide range of applications including electronics/electrical components, electrical insulator[1].

The inclusion of nanoscale carbon-based fillers such as carbon nanofibers, carbon nanotubes, grapheme/graphite nanoplatelets, and carbon blacks into insulating epoxy resins have allowed to obtain electrically conductive nanocomposites in accompanying with unique mechanical and multi-functional properties. Accordingly, epoxy-based composites reinforced with carbon-based nanofillers have been extensively investigated for the uses in advanced areas.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

2.1 Materials

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA, YD-128, Kukdo Chemical (Kunshan) co., Ltd.) and 2,3,6-Tetrahydro-3-methylphthalic anhydride (H-316, Chuzhou Hui-sheng Electronic Materials Co.,

Ltd.) and 2101CN liquid-type imidazole (Chuzhou Hui-sheng Electronic Materials Co., Ltd.) are used as polymer matrix and hardener and accelerator for the thermosetting epoxy resin matrix, respectively. Pristine MWCNT purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Inc. with an average diameter of 4.5-10 nm and length of $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$, which was produced by Catalytic Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) Method was been dispersed in resin matrix as conductive reinforcing nanofiller.

2.2 Preparation of conductive composite films

Epoxy-based composite films were fabricated by a calendaring approach, an efficient film-casting and following thermal-curing. First, acetone solutions as solvent including resin were stirred for 10 min to reduce the viscosity of the mixture. Then, different contents MWCNT (0.0-2.0 wt% of the matrix and hardener) were added in acetone/resin solutions and were stirred on hot plates at 80 °C for 4 h to pre-mixing mixture and to remove the solvent. Second, the MWCNT/resin mixture was post-dispersing by a 3-roll mill. Because the initial MWCNT agglomerates are quite large the MWCNT/epoxy mixture is first processed at a large gap, $\delta_g = 15 \mu\text{m}$, for at least five times and at the smaller gap setting of 5 μm the mixture was passed through 10 times. Third, the mixture was degassed at 80 °C for 1 h to eliminate the entrapped air. The hardener and accelerator were then added in the mixtures. The ratio of the accelerator and hardener to the epoxy was adjusted to be 2:80:100 by wt%. Subsequently, the mixtures were cast on a polyimide film, which were placed between aluminum plates. Finally, the mixtures were thermally cured at 100 °C for 2 h, 120 °C for 2 h, 140 °C for 4 h. The thickness of the final composite films was $\sim 700 \mu\text{m}$. The fabricated composite film samples were named for MWCNT/EP_X, where X denotes the MWCNT content by wt%.

2.3 Characterization

Electrical current (I) and electrical power (P) of the composite samples with different MWCNT contents was measured as a function of applied voltage (V) of 1-90 V by using power analyzer (AITEK, AWS2103). Electric heating behavior of the composite films was characterized with a digital thermometer (MASTECH, MS6511). For the electrical experiments, films samples with 5.0 mm width and the distance between two crocodile clips was kept at 10.0 mm. Conductive sliver was pasted to the ends of the sample to decrease the contact resistance efficiently. The thermal conductivity was also measured by a thermal conductivity meter (XIATECH, TC 3000E).

3 REDUCTION AND DISSCUSSION

3.1 Electrical and Thermal Properties

Electrical properties of MWCNT/EP composite samples were investigated as functions of MWCNT content and applied voltage. Figure 1 Shows current-voltage (I - V) curves of the composite samples containing different MWCNT contents. For the MWCNT/EP_0, no electrical current was detected over the applied voltage range of 1-90 V. This is due to the sample with the insulation resistivity of $\sim 10^{16} \Omega \text{cm}$. For the composite samples with MWCNT contents of 0.01wt% -0.03 wt% with the electrical resistivity of $\sim 10^5 \Omega \text{cm}$, there is a weak electrical current over the applied voltage, which provides the samples exist a rather low percolation threshold. On the other hand, the electrical current of the composite samples with MWCNT contents of 0.01-2.0 wt% increased linearly with the applied voltage and the slopes of the I - V curves were steeper for the composite samples with higher MWCNT content. It demonstrates that the electrical transport properties of MWCNT/EP composite samples with 0.01-2.0 wt% exhibit linear behavior by obeying Ohm's law. For the MWCNT/EP_1.0, the I - V curve shows non-Ohmic behavior in the high-applied voltage range. This non-Ohmic behavior is most likely due to a tunneling mechanism. The tunneling mechanism predicts that conduction may occur by electron hopping from a carbon nanotube to an adjacent one when they are close enough. The electric current flows through the direct contact of carbon nanotube networks under low voltage by obeying percolation theory, with increasing the applied voltage, the current and temperature increase obviously during Joule heating. The Joule heating allows the execution of hopping, which led to an

increasingly effective dimensionality and narrow width of the gaps among the carbon nanotube, thus the I - V curves deviate from the Ohmic behavior.

Figure 1: current-voltage (I - V) curves for the composite films with different MWCNT contents

The electrical resistance (R) of MWCNT/EP composite samples was evaluated from the slopes of I - V curves in Figure 1 and it plotted as a function of MWCNT contents, as shown in Figure 2. By using the relation of $R=\rho(L/A)$, where L is the sample length between crocodile clips and A is the cross-sectional area of a composite sample, the electrical resistivity ρ of the composite samples could be calculated and the result was also presented as a function of MWCNT content, as can be seen in Figure 2. The electrical resistivity was dependent on MWCNT content by showing a typical percolation behavior. It was found that the electrical resistivity decreased dramatically from $\sim 10^{15} \Omega \text{ cm}$ for the MWCNT/EP_0 to $\sim 10^2 \Omega \text{ cm}$ for the MWCNT/EP_2. To determine the electrical percolation threshold, the following power law relation can be used

$$\sigma \propto (p - p_c)^t \quad (1)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity (the inverse of electrical resistivity), p is the MWCNT volume fraction, p_c is the critical volume fraction at electrical percolation, and t is the critical exponent. The straight line with $p_c = 0.014 \text{ vol}\%$ ($\sim 0.018 \text{ wt}\%$) and $t = 1.34$ gives a good fit to the experimental data of $\log \sigma$ versus $\log (p - p_c)$ (inset of Figure 2). The critical exponent provides an index of the system dimensionality, and theoretical values of 1.3 and 1.94 have been predicted for ideal 2-D and 3-D systems, respectively. Thus, the t value of 1.34 for the MWCNT/EP composite samples indicates that MWCNTs form a 2-D network at the percolation threshold of $\sim 0.018 \text{ wt}\%$ MWCNT. In addition, it should be mentioned that the MWCNT/EP composite samples with low electrical resistivity less than $\sim 10^8 \Omega \text{ cm}$ can be utilized as ESD and/or EMI shielding materials for electronic devices and components.

Figure 2: electrical resistance and resistivity of MWCNT/EP composite films as a function of the MWCNT content. Inset is a log-log plot of electrical conductivity versus volume fraction of MWCNT.

Figure 3 shows the thermal conductivity results and linear curve fits for varying concentrations of carbon nanotubes. Unlike electrical conductivity, a typical percolation behavior is seen, the increase in thermal conductivity with increasing nanotube concentration. For the MWCNT/EP_2.0, the thermal conductivity only increases ~ 20% over the neat epoxy. This may be that carbon nanotubes interact with resin matrix weakly on the interface, which leads to the large thermal resistance.

Figure 3: Influence of carbon nanotubes on composite thermal conductivity

3.2 Electric Heating Behavior

Figure 4: Time-dependent temperature changes of MWCNT/EP composite films at different applied voltages of 1-90V: (A) MWCNT/EP_0.05; (B)MWCNT/EP_0.07; (C)MWCNT/EP_1; (D) MWCNT/EP_2

For the composite samples with MWCNT contents of 0.05-2.0 wt%, electric heating experiments were carried out by varying applied voltage of 1-90 V. Figure 4 presents the time-dependent temperature changes of the composite films with different MWCNT contents at various applied voltages. In the case of the MWCNT/EP_0.05, the temperature increased rapidly when a voltage above ~20 V was applied at 5 s, reached a maximum value within ~30 s, and decreased quickly to room temperature when the applied voltage was off at 120 s. The maximum temperature was found to increase with the increment of the applied voltage. This electric heating behavior was also detected for other composite samples with higher MWCNT contents of 0.07-2.0 wt%, except the result that the maximum temperatures at different applied voltage were even higher for the composite samples with higher MWCNT contents.

Time dependent temperature curves in Figure 4 can be divided into three region: the temperature growth (heating) region (5-30 s), the equilibrium (maximum temperature) region (30-120 s), and the temperature decay (cooling) region (120-200 s). In the first region, the temperature growth with time can be empirically expressed as

$$\left(\frac{T_t - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right) = 1 - e^{-t/\tau_g} \quad (2)$$

Where T_0 and T_m are the initial and maximum temperature, respectively. T_t is an arbitrary temperature at time t . τ_g is the characteristic growth time constant. For all the composite samples showing electric heating behavior, the τ_g values could be calculated by fitting the data in the first stage of temperature versus time plots, and they are listed in Table 1. It was found that the τ_g values were not dependent on the MWCNT content within the experimental error. On the other hand, the average τ_g value of 8.05 ± 0.65 s for all the composite samples is far lower than the ones for ceramic

superconductor /butyl rubber and is close to other carbon series filler-reinforced polymer composites reported in literature. It indicates that MWCNT/EP composite samples exhibit unusually rapid temperature responses to applied voltages.

In the second region in equilibrium, heat gain by electric power is equal to heat loss by radiation and convection according to the conservation law of energy. The heat transferred by radiation and convection, h_{r+c} is express as

$$h_{r+c} = \frac{I_c V_0}{T_m - T_0} \quad (3)$$

Where I_c is the steady state current and V_0 is the initial applied voltage. Accordingly, the h_{r+c} values could be calculated by the data in the equilibrium region. The h_{r+c} values were generally higher for the composite samples with higher MWCNT contents. In addition, the average h_{r+c} values of 4.88 ± 0.68 for the all composite samples is quite lower than the values reported for other filler-reinforced polymer composite systems, Which demonstrates that MWCNT/EP composite samples have high electric heating efficiency by requiring relatively low electric power to maintain a maximum temperature.

In the third region, during which the applied voltage was off, the composite samples were left to cool down by radiation and convection according to Newton's law of cooling. Therefore, the temperature decreases with time, which can be described by the following empirical formula:

$$\left(\frac{T_t - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right) = e^{-t/\tau_d} \quad (4)$$

where τ_d is the decay time constant. The τ_d values were calculated by fitting temperature decay with time in the temperature decay (cooling) region, and they are also listed in Table 1. For all the composite samples with 0.05-2.0 wt% MWCNT, the average value of τ_d was estimated to be 10.79 ± 1.09 s, which also supports that MWCNT/EP composite samples show efficient cooling behavior.

Table 1: Characteristic parameters for electric heating performance of MWCNT/EP composite films under applied voltages

Composite samples	Filler content (wt%)	Voltage (V)	τ_g (s)	h_{r+c} (mW/°C)	τ_d (s)
MWCNTs/epoxy	0.05	10-90	9.31±0.53	3.97±0.17	12.61±0.73
	0.07	10-90	7.99±0.41	4.71±1.06	9.23±2.03
	0.1	10-90	8.06±0.56	4.42±0.39	10.49±0.63
	0.3	10-90	7.46±0.53	4.66±0.46	10.24±0.24
	0.5	10-90	8.43±0.98	5.25±0.78	11.68±0.73
	0.7	10-60	7.42±0.54	4.37±0.88	10.18±1.09
	1	10-50	8.29±0.66	5.73±1.63	11.7±0.60
	2	10-40	7.42±0.74	5.90±0.80	10.22±1.16
Graphene/epoxy [2]	5	10-70	3.36±0.67	2.2±0.5	5.84±2.38
Graphene/MWCNT/epo-xy[1]	5	10-40	8.1±0.7	4.2±2.6	10.3±3.2
MWCNTs/polyethylene[3]	10	10-30	15.35±1.48	15.7±3.5	-
Ceramic superconductor/butyl rubber[4]	10	10	196.2	83000	197.4

9 CONCLUSIONS

MWCNT/EP composite samples were prepared by an efficient films-casting and following thermal-curing were of DGEBA/hardener mixtures containing 0.01-2.0 wt%. The electrical resistivity of composite films varies from $\sim 10^{16}$ Ω cm for the neat composite films to $\sim 10^2$ Ω cm of the composite films with 2.0 wt % MWCNTs owing to the formation of a conductive two-dimensional network of MWCNTs. It was found that the excellent electric heating performance and operational stability of the

MWCNT/EP composite samples in terms of rapid temperature response and high electric power efficiency is associated with the effective conductive paths formed by MWCNTs. Overall, it is highly expected that the composite samples can be efficiently used for floor heating films, which do not require high temperature above 100 °C.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No.11302054, 11532013) and Natural Science Foundation of Heilongjiang Province of China (No.A2015012).

REFERENCES

- [1] Jeong, Young Gyu, and Ji-Eun An. Effects of mixed carbon filler composition on electric heating behavior of thermally-cured epoxy-based composite films. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* , **56** (2014): 1-7.
- [2] An, Ji-Eun, and Young Gyu Jeong. Structure and electric heating performance of graphene/epoxy composite films, *European Polymer Journal*, **49.6**(2013): 1322-1330.
- [3] Isaji, Setsuko, Yuezhen Bin, and Masaru Matsuo. Electrical conductivity and self-temperature-control heating properties of carbon nanotubes filled polyethylene films, *Polymer* , **50.4**(2009): 1046-1053.
- [4] El-Tantawy, Farid. Joule heating treatments of conductive butyl rubber/ceramic superconductor composites: a new way for improving the stability and reproducibility?, *European polymer journal*, **37.3** (2001): 565-574.